

Multiplexer based Power Saving Flexible Filter Bank for Digital Hearing Aid applications

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Abstract

Power drain is one of the common issue in almost all electronic gadgets. Here a multiplexer based power efficient filter bank is presented. Digital Hearing aid design requires a bank of filters that provides reasonable audiogram matching for a specific case of hearing loss. Many a fixed and reconfigurable filter banks are reported for different types of sound wave decomposition plans for audiogram matching. But the delay and hardware complexity of these structures are relatively large for a compact hearing aid system. In this paper, a minimum phase constrained least square finite impulse response filter bank with reduced group delay and with hardware flexibility is proposed. Minimum phase FIR filter shows least passband group delay among the group of stable filters with same magnitude response characteristics and the coefficients required for filter is only half of that of the prototype finite impulse response filter. Multiplications per sample is considerably reduced in this method and is suitable for systems where the spectra of desired and noise signals are overlapped. The proposed filter bank can operate in two modes. In one mode the number of filters per bank is seven and in the other power saving mode it is six. Synthesis result of the proposed design is also presented.

Keywords - Minimum phase filter; finite impulse response filter; multiplexer; audiogram; hearing loss

1. INTRODUCTION

Power efficiency and compactness are the key features of a digital hearing aid in now a days. People are generally concerned about the heating effect and aesthetics of the device. Filter bank plays an important role in selecting and processing the sound signals picked up by the microphone. Filter bank act as the primary structural tool for processing sound, it divides the incoming sound in to multiple frequency bands, allowing the device to treat different parts of audio spectrum independently. Most people with hearing loss don't lose hearing capability equally across all frequencies. The Filter bank amplifies the signals at different levels of volume for each band to compensate the raised hearing thresholds. The digital hearing aid Filter banks can be classified as uniform and non-uniform types [1-6]. Nonuniform Filter banks are preferred in most cases because nonuniform bands mimic the human ear's logarithmic nature, offering more precision at lower frequency range where the speech quality is most critical. Delays of the order of 10 ms in the device will result disturbing effect for

hearing aid users. Hardware requirement, power consumption and delay are the critical parameters to be considered for the design of a compact digital hearing aid.

Digital hearing aid Filter banks are usually designed by uniform and nonuniform filters. Nonuniform filter banks match better as human ear shows nonuniform frequency resolution properties. Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) Filter bank has low computation complexity but filter bank with Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter is a better option due to linear phase characteristic, stability and regular structure of the system. Design of low-power ANSI S1.11 filter bank structure for digital hearing aids is reported in [1]. Long group delay and sharp filter parameters are the main drawbacks of this system. Customer will be disturbed by the hearing aid delay if it is more than 10 ms. FIR reconfigurable filter bank with reduced computational complexity is presented in [2] in which decimation, interpolation, and frequency response masking methods are used. In this design, the hardware complexity is reduced at the expense of longer delay, greater than 20ms. Long delays will cause many problems such as the difference between hearing aid produced and direct received sound, etc.

A nonlinear reconfigurable filter bank is proposed in [3] by Huang et al. Variable bandwidth digital filter for audiogram matching with Farrow structure is proposed in [4], in which Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic precision is compromised to reduce the hardware. In this case, additional accumulator circuitry is required to vary the tunable factor value and which will result in a further increase in complexity of the structure. A reconfigurable filter bank with linear phase filter symmetry property and fractional interpolation is reported in [5]. A nonuniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) filter bank is proposed in [6] in which separate filter orders are used for different bands. A filter bank structure with constrained least square (CLS) FIR filter for audiogram matching in digital hearing aids is presented in [7], in which multiplier requirement is so high as the order of filter is large. Fractional interpolation technique is used for filter banks used in [8]. In this method hardware is reduced but the delay is increased up to 12.9 ms. Reconfigurable filter bank for digital hearing aid with IoT is reported in [9]. Cosine modulation and Frequency warping techniques are the methods used for the filter bank design in [10]. Delay and Hardware complexity are relatively low in this design.

From literature review, it is evident that it is not easy to tradeoff between delay and hardware complexity of filter banks for digital hearing aid devices. In this work, a filter bank with minimum phase filter derived from constrained least square

(CLS) FIR filter, is proposed. In a minimum phase filter, the number of coefficients is only half of that of the prototype FIR filter. So hardware requirement of the filter is reduced drastically without any effect on magnitude response characteristics. In the multiplexer based design, two types of filter banks are used. In Mode (0), seven band filter is selected and in Mode (1), six band filter is selected. Power consumption is reduced in Mode (1), because only six filters are used in the filter structure. Minimum phase filter's passband group delay is very much small compared to that of linear phase FIR filter with the same characteristics. This property of the filter helps to preserve the envelope fidelity of speech signal. In a noisy environment, envelope fidelity is an important factor in determining the intelligibility and quality of speech [11]. Minimum phase filter exhibit small variations in phase in the passband but studies in psychoacoustics have reported that the sensitivity of human ear to such small phase distortions is very low. Experiments conducted by Lipshitz et al, reported in [12] states that such minute phase variations on speech signals and normal music are not at all audible by humans. The filter bank structures are synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL compiler v1.10 software. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response.

The paper is organized as follows. An overview of minimum phase constrained least square FIR filters is given in Section II. Hearing loss and audiogram are discussed in Section III, Filter bank structure implementation and audiogram matching are presented in Section IV, performance evaluation is reported in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

2. MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

2.1 CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

In Constrained least square FIR filter, it is possible to design FIR filters without explicitly specifying transition widths for the magnitude response. This approach is more suitable for the situations where signal information and noise appear together in the same frequency band. Upper and lower thresholds for maximum allowable ripple in the magnitude response of the filter are defined in this technique [13-15]. Here, least square error minimization technique is applied not only to specific bands but over the whole frequency range of the filter response. The overall error minimization includes areas of discontinuity in the ideal filter response. The integral square error includes the region around cut off frequency and avoids Gibb's phenomenon without using windowing operation. The frequency response of FIR filter can be represented as

$$H(\omega) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} h(n)e^{-j\omega n} \quad (1)$$

If $h(n) = h(N - 1 - n)$, then $H(\omega)$ has linear phase and can be written as

$$H(\omega) = C(\omega)e^{-jM\omega} \quad (2)$$

where $C(\omega)$ is the real valued amplitude, and $M = \frac{(N-1)}{2}$ for filter of length N . For symmetric odd length filters $C(\omega)$ can be represented as

$$C(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c(0) + \sum_{n=1}^M c(n) \cos n\omega \quad (3)$$

Where the impulse response coefficients $h(n)$, in terms of the cosine coefficients $c(n)$ are

$$h(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} c(M - n) & \text{for } 0 \leq n \leq M - 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} c(0) & \text{for } n = M \\ \frac{1}{2} c(n - M) & \text{for } M + 1 \leq n \leq N - 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Let $D(\omega)$ be the desired amplitude of an ideal lowpass filter. Approximating this discontinuous function by the cosine polynomial $C(\omega)$ is the fundamental filter design problem. The approximation error can be written as

$$E(\omega) = D(\omega) - C(\omega) \quad (5)$$

The primary measures of approximation used in filter design are

i) The weighted integral square error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_2 = \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi W(\omega) (C(\omega) - D(\omega))^2 d\omega \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

ii)The weighted Chebyshev error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_\infty = \max_{\omega \in [0, \pi]} |W(\omega)(C(\omega) - D(\omega))| \quad (7)$$

where $W(\omega)$ is a nonnegative error weighting function. The simplest method to design optimal FIR filters is to minimize the term $\|C(\omega) - D(\omega)\|_2$.

The CLS FIR filter design minimizes the unweighted integral square error with the constraint that local minima and maxima of $C(\omega)$ lie within the specified lower and upper bound functions $K_L(\omega)$ and $K_U(\omega)$. The lower and upper bound functions are given by

$$K_L(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 - \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ -\delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$K_U(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 + \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ \delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where δ_p and δ_s are the maximum allowed deviations in the passband and stopband. This method of filter design is more suitable for situation where the maximum peak error size is to

be controlled and the input signals to be filtered have energy in the transition band.

2.2 MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

Higher order Linear Phase FIR filter has narrow transition band and has very long group delay which is proportional to the filter order. In hearing aid applications, such a long delay is not at all favorable. By the minor relaxation in linear phase characteristics, design of FIR filter with lower order can be possible. This will in turn reduce the overall group delay and also reduce the cost by saving the number of multipliers required for the filter bank. Minimum phase filter group delay has the smallest value among the family of filters with the same magnitude response characteristics. A stable causal filter is treated as minimum phase filter if all of its zeros are inside the unit circle [13]. Consider a FIR transfer function of degree M

$$H(z) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(n)z^{-n} \quad (10)$$

The mirror image polynomial of H(z) is given by

$$\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M}H(z^{-1}) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(M-n)z^{-n} \quad (11)$$

The zeros of $\hat{H}(z)$ are reciprocal to that of H(z). As a result

$$K(z) = H(z)\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M}H(z)H(z^{-1}) \quad (12)$$

K(z) has zeros with mirror image symmetry in z plane and is thus a Type I linear phase transfer function with order 2M. K(z) has double zeros on the unit circle and is thus factorizable to H(z) and $\hat{H}(z)$. From the equation (12), the magnitude squared function can be represented as

$$|H(e^{j\omega})|^2 = K(\omega) \quad (13)$$

Amplitude response of K(z) is thus non negative. It is also clear that, K(ω) has double zeros on [0,π] interval as K(z) has double zeros on the unit circle. Based on this logic a minimum phase filter can be obtained by using the following procedure [16, 17]. Step1: Design a Type I linear phase FIR transfer function E(z) of degree 2M, with the amplitude response $\hat{E}(\omega)$ specifications

$$1 - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$-\delta_s(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq \delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

E(z) has only a single unit circle zero .

Step 2: Determination of the linear phase transfer function

$$K(z) = \delta_s(E) z^{-M} + E(z) \quad (14)$$

Its amplitude response $\hat{K}(\omega)$ satisfies the relation

$$1 + \delta_s(E) - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_s(E) + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$0 \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 2\delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

It is evident that, K(z) has double zeros in the stop band along with all other zeros situated with a mirror image symmetry. Thus K(z) can be expressed as

$$K(z) = z^{-M}H(z)H(z^{-1}) \quad (15)$$

Here H(z) is a minimum phase FIR transfer function which contains the zeros of K(z) that are inside unit circle and one from each of the double zeros of K(z) on the unit circle.

Step3: Use spectral factorization to determine H(z) from K(z).

In the direct method, minimum phase filter is obtained by selecting the zeros of K(z) that are inside the unit circle The pass band ripple $\delta_p(E)$ and the stop band ripple $\delta_s(E)$ of E(z) have to ensure that the specified pass band ripple δ_p and stop band ripple δ_s of H(z) are satisfied accurately. It can be shown that

$$\delta_p(E) = \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta_p}{1 + \delta_s}} - 1 \quad (16)$$

$$\delta_s(E) = \sqrt{\frac{2\delta_s}{1 + \delta_s}} \quad (17)$$

Non linear IIR filters with smaller group delay can be possible, but such filters are not at all stable. The number of coefficients in a minimum phase filter is reduced to half of that of the prototype FIR filter. Smaller group delay can be achieved in the passband region by using stable minimum phase FIR filters with low hardware complexity. Minimum phase filters are always stable because all poles of the system are inside the unit circle. In the proposed design constrained least square FIR Filter is used as the prototype FIR filter to derive minimum phase FIR filter.

2.3 MULTIPLEXER BASED FILTER BANK ARCHITECTURE

In the proposed design, the filter bank architecture has two modes, for mod M(0) there will be seven active filters in the filter bank and in mod M(1) there will be only six active filters in the filter bank. A 2:1multiplexer is used for this purpose. The structure of the proposed filter bank is shown in Figure 1. A 2:1multiplexer using logic gates is shown in Figure 2. When M=0, first AND gate is enabled and the second AND gate is disabled. So the input X₁ will be transferred to the output terminal Y. Similarly, when M=1, first AND gate is disabled and the second AND gate is enabled. So the input X₂ will be transferred to the output terminal Y. Mode M(1) may be selected to save the power, as the number of filters is reduced, this mode will consume less power. The audiogram matching error of Mode (1) is slightly higher than that of Mode (0), but within the tolerable limit of 3 dB. A Multiplexer can be realized using basic logic gates as shown in Figure 2. When M = 0, output of the filter bank with seven filters is selected and for M = 1, output of the filter bank with six filters is selected.

Fig. 1. Proposed filter bank structure

M	Y
0	X ₁
1	X ₂

Fig. 2. Multiplexer (2:1) using logic gates

3. AUDIOGRAM AND HEARING LOSS

Audiometric testing is used to measure the hearing ability of a person and a chart of this measurement is known as Audiogram. The softest sound a person can hear at specific audio frequency band is termed as threshold of hearing. Audiogram of a person with normal level of hearing is shown in Figure 3. Here, Y axis represents the ear response measured in decibels (dB) and corresponding frequency in Hertz (Hz) is plotted in X axis. Generally, thresholds upto 20 dB are treated as normal hearing level. Symbols ‘O’ and ‘X’ used in the audiogram represents the response of right ear and left ear respectively. In a standard audiogram, hearing level measurements are usually carried out at octave frequencies (250/500/1k/2k/4k/8k). A hearing impaired person’s sensitivity is low at certain frequency bands and this hearing loss is rectified by the selective amplification of sound signals at the respective band of frequencies. Reference audiograms used in this work are selected from the website of independent hearing aid information source <http://www.earinfo.com>. Response of hearing aid filter bank should match the audiogram of affected patient to compensate the hearing loss by selective amplification of audio signals. Audiogram of mild hearing loss at high frequencies is used in this paper for the analysis of hardware complexity, delay and matching error. Matching error

is defined as the maximum overall error between filter bank response and the audiogram of a specific hearing loss case. Matching error 3dB is considered as the maximum tolerable limit, because psycho acoustical studies have shown that [11,12], people are generally not sensitive to errors less than 3dB.

Fig. 3 Audiogram for normal hearing

4 CLS FIR FILTER BANK AND AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

The basic architecture of a filter bank with N number of filters is shown in Figure 3. CLS FIR filter of order $n = 32$, $\delta_p = 10^{-5}$, $\delta_s = 10^{-5}$ is used as the prototype filter for the design of minimum phase filter bank structure. The smooth transition band characteristic of minimum phase CLS FIR filter enables to reduce filter order and number of bands required for audiogram matching.

Fig. 3 Minimum phase Filter Bank structure

In the proposed design, the filter bank architecture has two modes, for mod $M(0)$ there will be seven active filters in the

filter bank and in mod $M(1)$ there will be only six active filters in the filter bank. A 2:1 multiplexer is used to select the modes. The individual band widths of filters used for filter bank design are shown in Table 1. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response. Frequency response of low pass minimum phase CLS FIR filter with cut off frequency 2 kHz is shown in Figure 4. Sampling frequency used for the filter design is 16 kHz and maximum pass band group delay of the filter is 0.493 ms. Group delay shows a slight variation from 5 to 8 samples in the pass band as shown in Figure 5. But this minor phase variation does not affect the hearing perception.

constrained least square FIR filter bank is proposed with low computational complexity and pass band group delay. Initially, sub band gain of the filter bank is taken as the midpoint value of a specific band of audiogram of a particular hearing loss case and then it is varied to get a minimum overall matching error. In this work, data broadcast structure is used for the filter bank, in which signals are transmitted to all the multipliers at the same time. By this structure, critical path can be reduced without pipelining latches and it will improve clock speed of the system [18]. Critical path represents the minimum time required to process a new sample.

Fig. 4. Frequency responses of a Minimum phase low pass filter.

Fig 5. Group delay of Minimum phase lowpass filter

Table 1: Frequency bands used

Hearing loss	No. of bands	Bandwidth (Hz)
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies.	6	550,1150,1100,1600,1520, 2850
	7	800,2100,1500,1200,1600,2400,1700

Number of coefficient multiplications required is only 17 for minimum phase filter derived from the CLS FIR filter with order 32. Pass band group delay and number of multipliers required for the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter are lower than the reported methods in literature. Audiogram matching for different filter orders are carried out and is plotted in Figure 6, minimum matching error is obtained for the filter bank structure with filter order 32 (17 coefficients). Hence minimum phase filter derived from CLS FIR filter with order $n = 32$ is selected for the design of proposed filter bank. High computational cost and long passband group delay are the two important drawbacks of FIR filter banks. This is mainly due to the requirement of large number of multipliers and which in turn is proportional to order of the filter. Here a minimum phase

Fig. 6 Matching Errors for different filter orders

4.1 AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

The filter bandwidths are selected by simulating filters individually in a filter bank for a minimum matching error. The stop band attenuation of the minimum phase CLS FIR Filter is 50 dB. Filter bank performance is evaluated by Matlab software and the gains and frequency bands of filters for audiogram matching are obtained by a number of simulation trials. In this work, the filter bank structure for matching audiogram pattern of mild hearing loss at high frequencies is designed. Figure 7(a)

represents audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies. Frequency response of 7 band filter bank (Mode (0)) is shown in Figure 7(b), the matching is shown in Figure 7(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 9(a) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.92 dB. Figure 8(b) represents frequency response of 6 band filter bank (Mode (1)), the matching is shown in Figure 8(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 9(b) and the maximum matching error obtained is 2.26 dB. Minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank is synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL Compiler v11.10 software. The area and power reports of Filter bank structure for audiogram matching of mild hearing loss at high frequencies is given in Table 2.

5. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In the proposed work, hardware requirement for the multiplication operation involved in the filter bank structure is reduced considerably. Battery performance and size of hearing aid mainly depends on power requirement and area of the filter bank structure used in the device. From the synthesis results of filter bank structures for matching of audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies, it is clear that there is considerable savings in area and power compared to the work [7]. So the proposed filter bank structures require less area and consumes less power, thus reduce hearing aid size and increase the battery life. Comparison of area utilization and power requirement is given in Figure 10. The passband group delay of the minimum phase CLS FIR filter used in the proposed method is lower than reported methods. Area utilization and power requirement increases with multipliers per filter in the filter bank structure. Performance comparisons of recently reported filter bank structures which are used for digital hearing aid design is given in the Table 3. Filter bank structure designed by Huang et al.[3] is based on non linear transformation and the number of multipliers/filter required is 187 and the delay is 7.77 ms. Farrow structure based variable bandwidth filter is reported in [4] in which the number of multipliers required per filter is 36 and the delay is 2.06 ms. Here precision of Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic is compromised to reduce the multiplier requirement. Fractional interpolation based filter bank structure proposed in [5], uses 74 multipliers/filter and the delay is 16.5ms. In the filter bank based on nonuniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) method reported by Sakthivel et al [6], complexity is expressed in terms of the filter order and generally the minimum number of multipliers required for n^{th} order filter is $(n + 1)$. In the method proposed by Swamy and Alex [9], delay is less than 10 ms but at the expense of increase in matching error, even greater than 4 dB in some cases. Second order frequency warping based filter bank by T Ma et al. consists of 73 multipliers and seven bands, the delay of the system is 7.13 ms. In the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank, the number of multipliers per filter is 17 and the maximum pass band group delay is only 0.493 ms which is the least among the reported methods. Matching errors of the proposed structure in Mode (0) and Mode (1) are within the tolerable limit value of 3 dB. Comparisons shows that the proposed filter bank structure has better performance than the reported methods. From the synthesis results it is clear that the proposed six band filter mode consumes low power than the seven band filter mode but with a slight increase in matching

error. Since area, delay and power requirement of the proposed structure is low, it is suitable for the design of compact low cost digital hearing aids. The proposed methods can be extended to other common hearing loss cases also.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank with 7 filters, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank with 6 filters, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Matching error for Mild hearing loss at high frequencies (a) Filter bank with 7 filters (b) Filter bank with 6 filters

Table 2 Synthesis results of Filter bank for Mild to Moderate hearing loss at low frequencies

	Mahesh[7]	Proposed M(0)	Proposed M(1)
Area (μm^2)	4424437.99	2230836.08	2230836.08
Power (nW)	513,682,049	224735950	182630860

Fig. 10 Comparison of (a) Area (b) Power

Table 3: Performance comparison

Hearing Loss	Method	Multipliers/ Filter	No. of bands	Delay (ms)	Matching Error (dB)
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	1.65
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	102	10	3.18	2.2
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	16.5	2.03
	Mahesh,Shahana[7]	74	10	2.25	1.82
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	0.98
	Swamy, Alex [9]	72	21	8.67	4.40
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	2.34
	Proposed M(0)	17	7	0.493	1.92
	Proposed M(1)	17	6	0.493	2.26

6. CONCLUSION

Compactness and power efficiency are the two parameters that supports the aesthetic design of hearing aids. Filter bank structure used in this work need less area and consume low power than the reported methods, hence suitable for the design of compact digital hearing aids. The reduction in multipliers per filter enables to reduce hardware requirement considerably in the proposed design. Based on the power status, the device can be switched between seven band filter mode and six band filter mode which require less power. The proposed minimum phase finite impulse response filter bank structure show very low pass band delay and matching error is also within the tolerable limit.

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